

Certain Notions of Single-Valued Neutrosophic K -Algebras

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Abstract

We apply the notion of single-valued neutrosophic sets to K -algebras. We develop the concept of single-valued neutrosophic K -subalgebras, and present some of their properties. Moreover, we study the behavior of single-valued neutrosophic K -subalgebras under homomorphism. Finally, we discuss $(\in, \in \vee q)$ -single-valued neutrosophic K -algebras.

Keywords: Single-valued neutrosophic sets, K -algebras, homomorphism, $(\in, \in \vee q)$ -single-valued neutrosophic K -algebras.

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1 Introduction

A new kind of logical algebra, known as K -algebra, was introduced by Dar and Akram [9]. A K -algebra was built on a group G by adjoining the induced binary operation on G . The group G is particularly of the type in which each non-identity element is not of order 2. This algebraic structure is, in general, non-commutative and non-associative with right identity element [5, 10, 11]. Akram et al [2–4] introduced fuzzy K -algebras. They then developed fuzzy K -algebras with other researchers worldwide. The concepts and results of K -algebras have been broadened to the fuzzy setting frames by applying Zadeh's fuzzy set theory and its generalizations, namely, interval-valued fuzzy sets, intuitionistic fuzzy sets, interval-valued intuitionistic fuzzy sets, bipolar fuzzy sets and vague sets.

In handling information regarding various aspects of uncertainty, non-classical logic (a great extension and development of classical logic) is considered to be a more powerful technique than the classical logic. The non-classical logic has nowadays become a useful tool in computer science. Moreover, non-classical logic deals with fuzzy information and uncertainty. In 1998, Smarandache [15] introduced neutrosophic sets as a generalization of fuzzy sets [19] and intuitionistic fuzzy sets [6]. A neutrosophic set is identified by three functions called truth-membership (T), indeterminacy-membership (I) and falsity-membership (F) whose values are real standard or non-standard subset of unit interval $]^{-0}, 1^{+}[$, where $^{-0} = 0 - \epsilon$, $1^{+} = 1 + \epsilon$, ϵ is an infinitesimal number. To apply neutrosophic set in real-life problems more conveniently, Smarandache [15] and Wang et al. [16] defined single-valued neutrosophic sets which takes the value from the subset of $[0, 1]$. Thus, a single-valued neutrosophic set is an instance of neutrosophic set, and can be used expediently to deal with real-world problems, especially in decision support. Algebraic structures have a vital place with vast applications in various disciplines. Neutrosophic set theory has been applied to algebraic structures [1, 8, 13]. In this research article, we introduce the notion of single-valued neutrosophic K -subalgebra and investigate some of their properties. We discuss K -subalgebra in terms of level sets using neutrosophic environment. We study the homomorphisms between

the single-valued neutrosophic K -subalgebras. We discuss characteristic K -subalgebras and fully invariant K -subalgebras. Finally, we discuss $(\in, \in \vee q)$ -single-valued neutrosophic K -algebras.

2 Single-Valued Neutrosophic K -algebras

The concept of K -algebra was developed by Dar and Akram in [14].

Definition 2.1. Let (G, \cdot, e) be a group in which each non-identity element is not of order 2. Then a K -algebra is a structure $\mathcal{K} = (G, \cdot, \odot, e)$ on a group G in which induced binary operation $\odot : G \times G \rightarrow G$ is defined by $\odot(x, y) = x \odot y = x.y^{-1}$ and satisfies the following axioms:

- (i) $(x \odot y) \odot (x \odot z) = (x \odot ((e \odot z) \odot (e \odot y))) \odot x$,
- (ii) $x \odot (x \odot y) = (x \odot (e \odot y)) \odot x$,
- (iii) $(x \odot x) = e$,
- (iv) $(x \odot e) = x$,
- (v) $(e \odot x) = x^{-1}$,

for all $x, y, z \in G$.

Definition 2.2. [16] Let Z be a space of objects with a general element $z \in Z$. A single-valued neutrosophic set \mathcal{A} in Z is characterized by three membership functions, $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}$ -truth membership function, $\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}$ -indeterminacy membership function and $\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}$ -falsity membership function, where $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(z), \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(z), \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(z) \in [0, 1]$, for all $z \in Z$.

That is $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}} : Z \rightarrow [0, 1], \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}} : Z \rightarrow [0, 1], \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}} : Z \rightarrow [0, 1]$ with no restriction on the sum of these three components. \mathcal{A} can also be written as $\mathcal{A} = \{ \langle z, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(z), \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(z), \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(z) \rangle \mid z \in Z \}$.

Definition 2.3. A single-valued neutrosophic set $\mathcal{A} = (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}})$ in a K -algebra \mathcal{K} is called a single-valued neutrosophic K -subalgebra of \mathcal{K} if it satisfy the following conditions:

- (a) $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(s \odot t) \geq \min\{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(s), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(t)\}$,
- (b) $\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(s \odot t) \geq \min\{\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(s), \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(t)\}$,
- (c) $\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(s \odot t) \leq \max\{\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(s), \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(t)\}$, for all $s, t \in G$.

Note that $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(e) \geq \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(s), \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(e) \geq \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(s), \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(e) \leq \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(s)$, for all $s \in G$.

Example 2.1. Consider $\mathcal{K} = (G, \cdot, \odot, e)$ be a K -algebra, where $G = \{e, x, x^2, x^3, x^4, x^5, x^6, x^7, x^8\}$ is the cyclic group of order 9 and Caley's table for \odot is given as:

\odot	e	x	x^2	x^3	x^4	x^5	x^6	x^7	x^8
e	e	x^8	x^7	x^6	x^5	x^4	x^3	x^2	x
x	x	e	x^8	x^7	x^6	x^5	x^4	x^3	x^2
x^2	x^2	x	e	x^8	x^7	x^6	x^5	x^4	x^3
x^3	x^3	x^2	x	e	x^8	x^7	x^6	x^5	x^4
x^4	x^4	x^3	x^2	x	e	x^8	x^7	x^6	x^5
x^5	x^5	x^4	x^3	x^2	x	e	x^8	x^7	x^6
x^6	x^6	x^5	x^4	x^3	x^2	x	e	x^8	x^7
x^7	x^7	x^6	x^5	x^4	x^3	x^2	x	e	x^8
x^8	x^8	x^7	x^6	x^5	x^4	x^3	x^2	x	e

We define a single-valued neutrosophic set $\mathcal{A} = (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}})$ in K -algebra as follows:

$$\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(e) = 0.8, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(e) = 0.7, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(e) = 0.4,$$

$$\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(s) = 0.2, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(s) = 0.3, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(s) = 0.6, \text{ for all } s \neq e \in G.$$

Clearly, $\mathcal{A} = (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}})$ is a single-valued neutrosophic K -subalgebra of \mathcal{K} .

Example 2.2. Consider $\mathcal{K} = (G, \cdot, \odot, e)$ be a K -algebra on dihedral group $D4$ given as $G = \{e, a, b, c, x, y, u, v\}$, where $c = ab, x = a^2, y = a^3, u = a^2b, v = a^3b$ and Caley's table for \odot is given as:

\odot	e	a	b	c	x	y	u	v
e	e	y	b	c	x	a	u	v
a	a	e	c	u	y	x	v	b
b	b	c	e	y	u	v	x	a
c	c	u	a	e	v	b	y	x
x	x	a	u	v	e	y	b	c
y	y	x	v	b	a	e	c	u
u	u	v	x	a	b	c	e	y
v	v	b	y	x	c	u	a	e

We define a single-valued neutrosophic set $\mathcal{A} = (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}})$ in K -algebra as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(e) &= 0.9, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(e) = 0.3, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(e) = 0.3, \\ \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(s) &= 0.6, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(s) = 0.2, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(s) = 0.4, \text{ for all } s \neq e \in G. \end{aligned}$$

By routine calculations, it can be verified that \mathcal{A} is a single-valued neutrosophic K -subalgebra of \mathcal{K} .

Proposition 2.1. If $\mathcal{A} = (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}})$ is a single-valued neutrosophic K -subalgebra of \mathcal{K} , then

- $(\forall s, t \in G), (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(s \odot t) = \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(t) \Rightarrow \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(s) = \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(e)).$
 $(\forall s, t \in G)(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(s) = \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(e) \Rightarrow \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(s \odot t) \geq \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(t)).$
- $(\forall s, t \in G), (\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(s \odot t) = \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(t) \Rightarrow \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(s) = \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(e)).$
 $(\forall s, t \in G)(\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(s) = \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(e) \Rightarrow \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(s \odot t) \geq \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(t)).$
- $(\forall s, t \in G), (\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(s \odot t) = \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(t) \Rightarrow \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(s) = \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(e)).$
 $(\forall s, t \in G)(\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(s) = \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(e) \Rightarrow \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(s \odot t) \leq \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(t)).$

Proof. 1. Assume that $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(s \odot t) = \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(t)$, for all $s, t \in G$. Taking $t = e$ and using (iii) of Definition 2.1, we have $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(s) = \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(s \odot e) = \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(e)$. Let for $s, t \in G$ be such that $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(s) = \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(e)$.

$$\text{Then } \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(s \odot t) \geq \min\{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(s), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(t)\} = \min\{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(e), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(t)\} = \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(t).$$

- Again assume that $\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(s \odot t) = \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(t)$, for all $s, t \in G$. Taking $t = e$ and by (iii) of Definition 2.1, we have $\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(s) = \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(s \odot e) = \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(e)$. Also let $s, t \in G$ be such that $\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(s) = \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(e)$.

$$\text{Then } \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(s \odot t) \geq \min\{\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(s), \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(t)\} = \min\{\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(e), \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(t)\} = \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(t).$$

- Consider that $\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(s \odot t) = \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(t)$, for all $s, t \in G$. Taking $t = e$ and again by (iii) of Definition 2.1, we have $\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(s) = \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(s \odot e) = \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(e)$. Let $s, t \in G$ be such that $\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(s) = \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(e)$.

$$\text{Then } \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(s \odot t) \leq \max\{\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(s), \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(t)\} = \max\{\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(e), \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(t)\} = \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(t).$$

This completes the proof. □

Definition 2.4. Let $\mathcal{A} = (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}})$ be a single-valued neutrosophic set in a K -algebra \mathcal{K} and let $(\alpha, \beta, \gamma) \in [0, 1] \times [0, 1] \times [0, 1]$ with $\alpha + \beta + \gamma \leq 3$. Then level subsets of \mathcal{A} are defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{A}_{(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)} &= \{s \in G \mid \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(s) \geq \alpha, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(s) \geq \beta, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(s) \leq \gamma\} \\ \mathcal{A}_{(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)} &= \{s \in G \mid \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(s) \geq \alpha\} \cap \{s \in G \mid \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(s) \geq \beta\} \cap \{s \in G \mid \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(s) \leq \gamma\} \\ \mathcal{A}_{(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)} &= \cup(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}, \alpha) \cap \cup'(\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}, \beta) \cap L(\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}, \gamma). \end{aligned}$$

are called (α, β, γ) -level subsets of single-valued neutrosophic set \mathcal{A} .

The set of all $(\alpha, \beta, \gamma) \in \text{Im}(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}) \times \text{Im}(\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}) \times \text{Im}(\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}})$ is known as image of $\mathcal{A} = (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}})$.

The set $\mathcal{A}_{(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)} = \{s \in G \mid \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(s) > \alpha, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(s) > \beta, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(s) < \gamma\}$ is known as strong (α, β, γ) -level subset of \mathcal{A} .

Proposition 2.2. If $\mathcal{A} = (\mathcal{T}_A, \mathcal{I}_A, \mathcal{F}_A)$ is a single-valued neutrosophic K -subalgebra of \mathcal{K} , then the level subsets $\cup(\mathcal{T}_A, \alpha) = \{s \in G \mid \mathcal{T}_A(s) \geq \alpha\}$, $\cup(\mathcal{I}_A, \beta) = \{s \in G \mid \mathcal{I}_A(s) \geq \beta\}$ and $L(\mathcal{F}_A, \gamma) = \{s \in G \mid \mathcal{F}_A(s) \leq \gamma\}$ are k -subalgebras of \mathcal{K} , for every $(\alpha, \beta, \gamma) \in \text{Im}(\mathcal{T}_A) \times \text{Im}(\mathcal{I}_A) \times \text{Im}(\mathcal{F}_A) \subseteq [0, 1]$, where $\text{Im}(\mathcal{T}_A)$, $\text{Im}(\mathcal{I}_A)$ and $\text{Im}(\mathcal{F}_A)$ are sets of values of $T(\mathcal{A})$, $\mathcal{I}(\mathcal{A})$ and $F(\mathcal{A})$, respectively.

Proof. Assume that $\mathcal{A} = (\mathcal{T}_A, \mathcal{I}_A, \mathcal{F}_A)$ is a single-valued neutrosophic K -subalgebra of \mathcal{K} and let $(\alpha, \beta, \gamma) \in \text{Im}(\mathcal{T}_A) \times \text{Im}(\mathcal{I}_A) \times \text{Im}(\mathcal{F}_A)$ be such that $\cup(\mathcal{T}_A, \alpha) \neq \emptyset$, $\cup(\mathcal{I}_A, \beta) \neq \emptyset$ and $L(\mathcal{F}_A, \gamma) \neq \emptyset$. Now to prove that \cup, \cup' and L are level K -subalgebras. Let for $s, t \in \cup(\mathcal{T}_A, \alpha)$, $\mathcal{T}_A(s) \geq \alpha$ and $\mathcal{T}_A(t) \geq \alpha$. It follows from Definition 3.1 that $\mathcal{T}_A(s \odot t) \geq \min\{\mathcal{T}_A(s), \mathcal{T}_A(t)\} \geq \alpha$. It implies that $s \odot t \in \cup(\mathcal{T}_A, \alpha)$. Hence $\cup(\mathcal{T}_A, \alpha)$ is a level K -subalgebra of \mathcal{K} . Similar result can be proved for $\cup'(\mathcal{I}_A, \beta)$ and $L(\mathcal{F}_A, \gamma)$. \square

Theorem 2.1. Let $\mathcal{A} = (\mathcal{T}_A, \mathcal{I}_A, \mathcal{F}_A)$ be a single-valued neutrosophic set in K -algebra \mathcal{K} . Then $\mathcal{A} = (\mathcal{T}_A, \mathcal{I}_A, \mathcal{F}_A)$ is a single-valued neutrosophic K -subalgebra of \mathcal{K} if and only if $\mathcal{A}_{(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)}$ is a K -subalgebra of \mathcal{K} , for every $(\alpha, \beta, \gamma) \in \text{Im}(\mathcal{T}_A) \times \text{Im}(\mathcal{I}_A) \times \text{Im}(\mathcal{F}_A)$ with $\alpha + \beta + \gamma \leq 3$.

Proof. Let $\mathcal{A} = (\mathcal{T}_A, \mathcal{I}_A, \mathcal{F}_A)$ be a single-valued neutrosophic set in a K -algebra \mathcal{K} . Assume that $\mathcal{A} = (\mathcal{T}_A, \mathcal{I}_A, \mathcal{F}_A)$ be a single-valued neutrosophic K -subalgebra of \mathcal{K} , i.e., the following three conditions of Definition 3.1 hold.

- $\mathcal{T}_A(s \odot t) \geq \min\{\mathcal{T}_A(s), \mathcal{T}_A(t)\}$,
- $\mathcal{I}_A(s \odot t) \geq \min\{\mathcal{I}_A(s), \mathcal{I}_A(t)\}$,
- $\mathcal{F}_A(s \odot t) \leq \max\{\mathcal{F}_A(s), \mathcal{F}_A(t)\}$, for all $s, t \in G$.
 $\mathcal{T}_A(e) \geq \mathcal{T}_A(s)$, $\mathcal{I}_A(e) \geq \mathcal{I}_A(s)$, $\mathcal{F}_A(e) \leq \mathcal{F}_A(s)$, for all $s \in G$.

Let for $(\alpha, \beta, \gamma) \in \text{Im}(\mathcal{T}_A) \times \text{Im}(\mathcal{I}_A) \times \text{Im}(\mathcal{F}_A)$ with $\alpha + \beta + \gamma \leq 3$ be such that $\mathcal{A}_{(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)} \neq \emptyset$. Let $s, t \in \mathcal{A}_{(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)}$ be such that

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{T}_A(s) &\geq \alpha, \mathcal{T}_A(t) \geq \alpha', \\ \mathcal{I}_A(s) &\geq \beta, \mathcal{I}_A(t) \geq \beta', \\ \mathcal{F}_A(s) &\leq \gamma, \mathcal{F}_A(t) \leq \gamma' .\end{aligned}$$

Without loss of generality we can assume that $\alpha \leq \alpha'$, $\beta \leq \beta'$ and $\gamma \geq \gamma'$. It follows from Definition 3.1 that

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{T}_A(s \odot t) &\geq \alpha = \min\{\mathcal{T}_A(s), \mathcal{T}_A(t)\}, \\ \mathcal{I}_A(s \odot t) &\geq \beta = \min\{\mathcal{I}_A(s), \mathcal{I}_A(t)\}, \\ \mathcal{F}_A(s \odot t) &\leq \gamma = \max\{\mathcal{F}_A(s), \mathcal{F}_A(t)\}.\end{aligned}$$

It implies that $s \odot t \in \mathcal{A}_{(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)}$. So, $\mathcal{A}_{(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)}$ is a K -subalgebra of \mathcal{K} . Conversely, we suppose that $\mathcal{A}_{(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)}$ is a K -subalgebra of \mathcal{K} . If the condition of the Definition 3.1 is not true, then there exist $u, v \in G$ such that

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{T}_A(u \odot v) &< \min\{\mathcal{T}_A(u), \mathcal{T}_A(v)\}, \\ \mathcal{I}_A(u \odot v) &< \min\{\mathcal{I}_A(u), \mathcal{I}_A(v)\}, \\ \mathcal{F}_A(u \odot v) &> \max\{\mathcal{F}_A(u), \mathcal{F}_A(v)\}.\end{aligned}$$

Taking

$$\begin{aligned}\alpha_1 &= \frac{1}{2}(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(u \odot v) + \min\{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(u), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(v)\}), \\ \beta_1 &= \frac{1}{2}(\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(u \odot v) + \min\{\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(u), \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(v)\}), \\ \gamma_1 &= \frac{1}{2}(\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(u \odot v) + \min\{\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(u), \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(v)\}).\end{aligned}$$

We have $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(u \odot v) < \alpha_1 < \min\{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(u), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(v)\}$, $\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(u \odot v) < \beta_1 < \min\{\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(u), \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(v)\}$ and $\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(u \odot v) > \gamma_1 > \max\{\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(u), \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(v)\}$. It implies that $u, v \in \mathcal{A}_{(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)}$ and $u \odot v \notin \mathcal{A}_{(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)}$, a contradiction. Therefore, the condition of Definition 3.1 is true. Hence $\mathcal{A} = (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}})$ is a single-valued neutrosophic k -subalgebra of \mathcal{K} . \square

Theorem 2.2. Let $\mathcal{A} = (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}})$ be a single-valued neutrosophic k -subalgebra and $(\alpha_1, \beta_1, \gamma_1), (\alpha_2, \beta_2, \gamma_2) \in \text{Im}(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}) \times \text{Im}(\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}) \times \text{Im}(\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}})$ with $\alpha_j + \beta_j + \gamma_j \leq 3$ for $j = 1, 2$. Then $\mathcal{A}_{(\alpha_1, \beta_1, \gamma_1)} = \mathcal{A}_{(\alpha_2, \beta_2, \gamma_2)}$ if $(\alpha_1, \beta_1, \gamma_1) = (\alpha_2, \beta_2, \gamma_2)$.

Proof. If $(\alpha_1, \beta_1, \gamma_1) = (\alpha_2, \beta_2, \gamma_2)$, then clearly $\mathcal{A}_{(\alpha_1, \beta_1, \gamma_1)} = \mathcal{A}_{(\alpha_2, \beta_2, \gamma_2)}$.

Assume that $\mathcal{A}_{(\alpha_1, \beta_1, \gamma_1)} = \mathcal{A}_{(\alpha_2, \beta_2, \gamma_2)}$. Since $(\alpha_1, \beta_1, \gamma_1) \in \text{Im}(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}) \times \text{Im}(\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}) \times \text{Im}(\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}})$, there exist $s \in G$ such that $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(s) = \alpha_1, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(s) = \beta_1$ and $\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(s) = \gamma_1$. It follows that $s \in \mathcal{A}_{(\alpha_1, \beta_1, \gamma_1)} = \mathcal{A}_{(\alpha_2, \beta_2, \gamma_2)}$. So that

$$\alpha_1 = \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(s) \geq \alpha_2, \beta_1 = \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(s) \geq \beta_2 \text{ and } \gamma_1 = \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(s) \leq \gamma_2.$$

Also $(\alpha_2, \beta_2, \gamma_2) \in \text{Im}(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}) \times \text{Im}(\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}) \times \text{Im}(\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}})$, there exist $t \in G$ such that $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(t) = \alpha_2, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(t) = \beta_2$ and $\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(t) = \gamma_2$. It follows that $t \in \mathcal{A}_{(\alpha_2, \beta_2, \gamma_2)} = \mathcal{A}_{(\alpha_1, \beta_1, \gamma_1)}$. So that $\alpha_2 = \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(t) \geq \alpha_1, \beta_2 = \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(t) \geq \beta_1$ and $\gamma_2 = \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(t) \leq \gamma_1$. Hence $(\alpha_1, \beta_1, \gamma_1) = (\alpha_2, \beta_2, \gamma_2)$. \square

Theorem 2.3. Let H be a K -subalgebra of K -algebra \mathcal{K} . Then there exist a single-valued neutrosophic K -subalgebra $\mathcal{A} = (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}})$ of K -algebra \mathcal{K} such that $\mathcal{A} = (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}) = H$, for some $\alpha, \beta \in (0, 1], \gamma \in [0, 1)$.

Proof. Let $\mathcal{A} = (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}})$ be a single-valued neutrosophic set in K -algebra \mathcal{K} given by

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(s) &= \begin{cases} \alpha \in (0, 1] & \text{if } s \in H, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \\ \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(s) &= \begin{cases} \beta \in (0, 1] & \text{if } s \in H, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \\ \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(s) &= \begin{cases} \gamma \in [0, 1) & \text{if } s \in H, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}\end{aligned}$$

Let $s, t \in G$. If $s, t \in H$, then $s \odot t \in H$ and so

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(s \odot t) &\geq \min\{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(s), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(t)\}, \\ \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(s \odot t) &\geq \min\{\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(s), \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(t)\}, \\ \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(s \odot t) &\leq \max\{\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(s), \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(t)\}.\end{aligned}$$

But if $s \notin H$ or $t \notin H$, then $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(s) = 0$ or $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(t), \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(s) = 0$ or $\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(t)$ and $\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(s) = 0$ or $\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(t)$. It follows that $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(s \odot t) \geq \min\{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(s), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(t)\}, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(s \odot t) \geq \min\{\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(s), \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(t)\}, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(s \odot t) \leq \max\{\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(s), \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(t)\}$.

Hence $\mathcal{A} = (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}})$ is a SVN K -subalgebra of \mathcal{K} . Consequently $\mathcal{A}_{(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)} = H$.

The above Theorem shows that any K -subalgebra of \mathcal{K} can be perceived as a level K -subalgebra of some single-valued neutrosophic K -subalgebras of \mathcal{K} . \square

Theorem 2.4. Let \mathcal{K} be a K -algebra. Given a chain of K -subalgebras: $\mathcal{A}_0 \subset \mathcal{A}_1 \subset \mathcal{A}_2 \subset \dots \subset \mathcal{A}_n = G$. Then there exist a single-valued neutrosophic K -subalgebra whose level K -subalgebras are exactly the K -subalgebras in this chain.

Proof. Let $\{\alpha_k \mid k = 0, 1, \dots, n\}, \{\beta_k \mid k = 0, 1, \dots, n\}$ be finite decreasing sequences and $\{\gamma_k \mid k = 0, 1, \dots, n\}$ be finite increasing sequence in $[0, 1]$ such that $\alpha_i + \beta_i + \gamma_i \leq 3$, for $i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, n$. Let $\mathcal{A} = (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}})$ be a single-valued neutrosophic set in \mathcal{K} defined by $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(\mathcal{A}_0) = \alpha_0, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(\mathcal{A}_0) = \beta_0, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(\mathcal{A}_0) = \gamma_0, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(\mathcal{A}_k \setminus \mathcal{A}_{k-1}) = \alpha_k, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(\mathcal{A}_k \setminus \mathcal{A}_{k-1}) = \beta_k$ and $\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(\mathcal{A}_k \setminus \mathcal{A}_{k-1}) = \gamma_k$, for $0 < k \leq n$. We claim that $\mathcal{A} = (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}})$ is a single-valued neutrosophic K -subalgebra of \mathcal{K} . Let $s, t \in G$. If $s, t \in \mathcal{A}_k \setminus \mathcal{A}_{k-1}$, then it implies that $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(s) = \alpha_k = \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(t), \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(s) = \beta_k = \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(t)$ and $\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(s) = \gamma_k = \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(t)$. Since each \mathcal{A}_k is a K -subalgebra, it follows that $s \odot t \in \mathcal{A}_k$. So that either $s \odot t \in \mathcal{A}_k \setminus \mathcal{A}_{k-1}$ or $s \odot t \in \mathcal{A}_{k-1}$. In any case, we conclude that

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(s \odot t) &\geq \alpha_k = \min\{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(s), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(t)\}, \\
\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(s \odot t) &\geq \beta_k = \min\{\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(s), \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(t)\}, \\
\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(s \odot t) &\leq \gamma_k = \max\{\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(s), \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(t)\}.
\end{aligned}$$

For $i > j$, if $s \in \mathcal{A}_i \setminus \mathcal{A}_{i-1}$ and $t \in \mathcal{A}_j \setminus \mathcal{A}_{j-1}$, then $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(s) = \alpha_i$, $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(t) = \alpha_j$, $\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(s) = \beta_i$, $\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(t) = \beta_j$ and $\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(s) = \gamma_i$, $\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(t) = \gamma_j$ and $s \odot t \in \mathcal{A}_i$ because \mathcal{A}_i is a K -subalgebra and $\mathcal{A}_j \subset \mathcal{A}_i$. It follows that

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(s \odot t) &\geq \alpha_i = \min\{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(s), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(t)\}, \\
\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(s \odot t) &\geq \beta_i = \min\{\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(s), \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(t)\}, \\
\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(s \odot t) &\leq \gamma_i = \max\{\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(s), \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(t)\}.
\end{aligned}$$

Thus, $\mathcal{A} = (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}})$ is a single-valued neutrosophic K -subalgebra of \mathcal{K} and all its non empty level subsets are level K -subalgebras of \mathcal{K} .

Since $\text{Im}(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}) = \{\alpha_0, \alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_n\}$, $\text{Im}(\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}) = \{\beta_0, \beta_1, \dots, \beta_n\}$, $\text{Im}(\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}) = \{\gamma_0, \gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_n\}$. Therefore, the level K -subalgebras of $\mathcal{A} = (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}})$ are given by the chain of K -subalgebras:

$$\begin{aligned}
\cup(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}, \alpha_0) &\subset \cup(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}, \alpha_1) \subset \dots \subset \cup(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}, \alpha_n) = G, \\
\cup'(\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}, \beta_0) &\subset \cup'(\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}, \beta_1) \subset \dots \subset \cup'(\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}, \beta_n) = G, \\
L(\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}, \gamma_0) &\subset L(\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}, \gamma_1) \subset \dots \subset L(\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}, \gamma_n) = G,
\end{aligned}$$

respectively. Indeed,

$$\begin{aligned}
\cup(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}, \alpha_0) &= \{s \in G \mid \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(s) \geq \alpha_0\} = \mathcal{A}_0, \\
\cup'(\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}, \beta_0) &= \{s \in G \mid \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(s) \geq \beta_0\} = \mathcal{A}_0, \\
L(\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}, \gamma_0) &= \{s \in G \mid \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(s) \leq \gamma_0\} = \mathcal{A}_0.
\end{aligned}$$

Now we prove that $\cup(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}, \alpha_k) = \mathcal{A}_k$, $\cup'(\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}, \beta_k) = \mathcal{A}_k$ and $L(\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}, \gamma_k) = \mathcal{A}_k$, for $0 < k \leq n$. Clearly, $\mathcal{A}_k \subseteq \cup(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}, \alpha_k)$, $\mathcal{A}_k \subseteq \cup'(\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}, \beta_k)$ and $\mathcal{A}_k \subseteq L(\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}, \gamma_k)$. If $s \in \cup(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}, \alpha_k)$, then $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(s) \geq \alpha_k$ and so $s \notin \mathcal{A}_i$, for $i > k$.

Hence $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(s) \in \{\alpha_0, \alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_k\}$ which implies that $s \in \mathcal{A}_i$, for some $i \leq k$ since $\mathcal{A}_i \subseteq \mathcal{A}_k$. It follows that $s \in \mathcal{A}_k$. Consequently, $\cup(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}, \alpha_k) = \mathcal{A}_k$ for some $0 < k \leq n$. Similar case can be proved for $\cup'(\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}, \beta_k) = \mathcal{A}_k$. Now if $t \in L(\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}, \gamma_k)$, then $\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(t) \leq \gamma_k$ and so $t \notin \mathcal{A}_i$, for some $j \leq k$. Thus, $\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(t) \in \{\gamma_0, \gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_k\}$ which implies that $t \in \mathcal{A}_j$, for some $j \leq k$. Since $\mathcal{A}_j \subseteq \mathcal{A}_k$. It follows that $t \in \mathcal{A}_k$.

Consequently, $L(\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}, \gamma_k) = \mathcal{A}_k$, for some $0 < k \leq n$. Hence the proof. \square

2.1 Homomorphism of single-valued neutrosophic K -algebras

Definition 2.5. Let $\mathcal{K}_1 = (G_1, \cdot, \odot, e_1)$ and $\mathcal{K}_2 = (G_2, \cdot, \odot, e_2)$ be two K -algebras and let ϕ be a function from \mathcal{K}_1 into \mathcal{K}_2 . If $\mathcal{B} = (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{B}}, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{B}}, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{B}})$ is a single-valued neutrosophic K -subalgebra of \mathcal{K}_2 , then the *preimage* of $\mathcal{B} = (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{B}}, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{B}}, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{B}})$ under ϕ is a single-valued neutrosophic K -subalgebra of \mathcal{K}_1 defined by $\phi^{-1}(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{B}})(s) = \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{B}}(\phi(s))$, $\phi^{-1}(\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{B}})(s) = \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{B}}(\phi(s))$ and $\phi^{-1}(\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{B}})(s) = \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{B}}(\phi(s))$, for all $s \in G_1$.

Theorem 2.5. Let $\phi : \mathcal{K}_1 \rightarrow \mathcal{K}_2$ be an epimorphism of K -algebras. If $\mathcal{B} = (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{B}}, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{B}}, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{B}})$ be a single-valued neutrosophic K -subalgebra of \mathcal{K}_2 , then $\phi^{-1}(\mathcal{B})$ be a single-valued neutrosophic K -subalgebra of \mathcal{K}_1 .

Proof. It is easy to see that $\phi^{-1}(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{B}})(e) \geq \phi^{-1}(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{B}})(s)$, $\phi^{-1}(\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{B}})(e) \geq \phi^{-1}(\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{B}})(s)$ and $\phi^{-1}(\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{B}})(e) \leq \phi^{-1}(\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{B}})(s)$ for all $s \in G_1$. Let $s, t \in G_1$, then

$$\begin{aligned}
\phi^{-1}(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{B}})(s \odot t) &= \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{B}}(\phi(s \odot t)) \\
\phi^{-1}(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{B}})(s \odot t) &= \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{B}}(\phi(s) \odot \phi(t)) \\
\phi^{-1}(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{B}})(s \odot t) &\geq \min\{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{B}}(\phi(s)), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{B}}(\phi(t))\} \\
\phi^{-1}(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{B}})(s \odot t) &\geq \min\{\phi^{-1}(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{B}})(s), \phi^{-1}(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{B}})(t)\}, \\
\\
\phi^{-1}(\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{B}})(s \odot t) &= \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{B}}(\phi(s \odot t)) \\
\phi^{-1}(\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{B}})(s \odot t) &= \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{B}}(\phi(s) \odot \phi(t)) \\
\phi^{-1}(\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{B}})(s \odot t) &\geq \min\{\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{B}}(\phi(s)), \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{B}}(\phi(t))\} \\
\phi^{-1}(\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{B}})(s \odot t) &\geq \min\{\phi^{-1}(\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{B}})(s), \phi^{-1}(\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{B}})(t)\}, \\
\\
\phi^{-1}(\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{B}})(s \odot t) &= \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{B}}(\phi(s \odot t)) \\
\phi^{-1}(\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{B}})(s \odot t) &= \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{B}}(\phi(s) \odot \phi(t)) \\
\phi^{-1}(\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{B}})(s \odot t) &\leq \max\{\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{B}}(\phi(s)), \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{B}}(\phi(t))\} \\
\phi^{-1}(\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{B}})(s \odot t) &\leq \max\{\phi^{-1}(\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{B}})(s), \phi^{-1}(\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{B}})(t)\}.
\end{aligned}$$

Hence $\phi^{-1}(\mathcal{B})$ is a single-valued neutrosophic K -subalgebra of \mathcal{K}_1 . □

Theorem 2.6. $\phi : \mathcal{K}_1 \rightarrow \mathcal{K}_2$ be an epimorphism of K -algebras. If $\mathcal{B} = (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{B}}, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{B}}, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{B}})$ is a single-valued neutrosophic K -subalgebra of \mathcal{K}_2 and $\mathcal{A} = (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}})$ is the *preimage* of \mathcal{B} under ϕ . Then \mathcal{A} is a single-valued neutrosophic K -subalgebra of \mathcal{K}_1 .

Proof. It is easy to see that $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(e) \geq \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(s)$, $\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(e) \geq \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(s)$ and $\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(e) \leq \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(s)$, for all $s \in G_1$. Now for any $s, t \in G_1$,

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(s \odot t) &= \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{B}}(\phi(s \odot t)) \\
\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(s \odot t) &= \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{B}}(\phi(s) \odot \phi(t)) \\
\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(s \odot t) &\geq \min\{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{B}}(\phi(s)), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{B}}(\phi(t))\} \\
\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(s \odot t) &\geq \min\{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(s), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(t)\}, \\
\\
\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(s \odot t) &= \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{B}}(\phi(s \odot t)) \\
\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(s \odot t) &= \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{B}}(\phi(s) \odot \phi(t)) \\
\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(s \odot t) &\geq \min\{\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{B}}(\phi(s)), \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{B}}(\phi(t))\} \\
\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(s \odot t) &\geq \min\{\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(s), \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(t)\}, \\
\\
\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(s \odot t) &= \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{B}}(\phi(s \odot t)) \\
\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(s \odot t) &= \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{B}}(\phi(s) \odot \phi(t)) \\
\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(s \odot t) &\leq \max\{\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{B}}(\phi(s)), \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{B}}(\phi(t))\} \\
\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(s \odot t) &\leq \max\{\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(s), \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(t)\}.
\end{aligned}$$

Hence \mathcal{A} is a single-valued neutrosophic K -subalgebra of \mathcal{K}_1 . □

Definition 2.6. Let a mapping $\phi : \mathcal{K}_1 \rightarrow \mathcal{K}_2$ from \mathcal{K}_1 into \mathcal{K}_2 of K -algebras and let $\mathcal{A} = (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}})$ be a single-valued neutrosophic set of \mathcal{K}_2 . The map $\mathcal{A} = (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}})$ is called the *preimage* of \mathcal{A} under ϕ , if $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}^{\phi}(s) = \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(\phi(s))$, $\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}^{\phi}(s) = \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(\phi(s))$ and $\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}^{\phi}(s) = \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(\phi(s))$ for all $s \in G_1$.

Proposition 2.3. Let $\phi : \mathcal{K}_1 \rightarrow \mathcal{K}_2$ be an epimorphism of K -algebras. If $\mathcal{A} = (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}})$ be a single-valued neutrosophic K -subalgebra of \mathcal{K}_2 , then $\mathcal{A}^{\phi} = (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}^{\phi}, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}^{\phi}, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}^{\phi})$ be a single-valued neutrosophic K -subalgebra of \mathcal{K}_1 .

Proof. For any $s \in G_1$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}^{\phi}(e_1) &= \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(\phi(e_1)) = \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(e_2) \geq \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(\phi(s)) = \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}^{\phi}(s), \\ \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}^{\phi}(e_1) &= \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(\phi(e_1)) = \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(e_2) \geq \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(\phi(s)) = \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}^{\phi}(s), \\ \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}^{\phi}(e_1) &= \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(\phi(e_1)) = \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(e_2) \leq \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(\phi(s)) = \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}^{\phi}(s).\end{aligned}$$

For any $s, t \in G_1$, since \mathcal{A} is a single-valued neutrosophic K -subalgebra of \mathcal{K}_2

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}^{\phi}(s \odot t) &= \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(\phi(s \odot t)) \\ \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}^{\phi}(s \odot t) &= \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(\phi(s) \odot \phi(t)) \\ \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}^{\phi}(s \odot t) &\geq \min\{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(\phi(s)), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(\phi(t))\} \\ \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}^{\phi}(s \odot t) &\geq \min\{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}^{\phi}(s), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}^{\phi}(t)\},\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}^{\phi}(s \odot t) &= \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(\phi(s \odot t)) \\ \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}^{\phi}(s \odot t) &= \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(\phi(s) \odot \phi(t)) \\ \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}^{\phi}(s \odot t) &\geq \min\{\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(\phi(s)), \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(\phi(t))\} \\ \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}^{\phi}(s \odot t) &\geq \min\{\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}^{\phi}(s), \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}^{\phi}(t)\},\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}^{\phi}(s \odot t) &= \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(\phi(s \odot t)) \\ \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}^{\phi}(s \odot t) &= \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(\phi(s) \odot \phi(t)) \\ \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}^{\phi}(s \odot t) &\leq \max\{\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(\phi(s)), \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(\phi(t))\} \\ \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}^{\phi}(s \odot t) &\leq \max\{\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}^{\phi}(s), \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}^{\phi}(t)\}.\end{aligned}$$

Hence $\mathcal{A}^{\phi} = (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}^{\phi}, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}^{\phi}, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}^{\phi})$ is a single-valued neutrosophic K -subalgebra of \mathcal{K}_1 . □

Proposition 2.4. Let $\phi : \mathcal{K}_1 \rightarrow \mathcal{K}_2$ be an epimorphism of K -algebras. If $\mathcal{A}^{\phi} = (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}^{\phi}, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}^{\phi}, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}^{\phi})$ be a single-valued neutrosophic K -subalgebra of \mathcal{K}_2 , then $\mathcal{A} = (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}})$ is a single-valued neutrosophic K -subalgebra of \mathcal{K}_1 .

Proof. Since there exist $s \in G_1$ such that $t = \phi(s)$, for any $t \in G_2$

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(t) &= \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(\phi(s)) = \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}^{\phi}(s) \leq \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}^{\phi}(e_1) = \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(\phi(e_1)) = \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(e_2), \\ \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(t) &= \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(\phi(s)) = \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}^{\phi}(s) \leq \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}^{\phi}(e_1) = \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(\phi(e_1)) = \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(e_2), \\ \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(t) &= \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(\phi(s)) = \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}^{\phi}(s) \geq \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}^{\phi}(e_1) = \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(\phi(e_1)) = \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(e_2).\end{aligned}$$

for any $s, t \in G_2$, $u, v \in G_1$ such that $s = \phi(u)$ and $t = \phi(v)$. It follows that

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(s \odot t) &= \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(\phi(u \odot v)) \\ \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(s \odot t) &= \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}^{\phi}(u \odot v) \\ \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(s \odot t) &\geq \min\{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}^{\phi}(u), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}^{\phi}(v)\} \\ \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(s \odot t) &\geq \min\{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(\phi(u)), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(\phi(v))\} \\ \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(s \odot t) &\geq \min\{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(s), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(t)\},\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(s \odot t) &= \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(\phi(u \odot v)) \\ \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(s \odot t) &= \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}^{\phi}(u \odot v) \\ \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(s \odot t) &\geq \min\{\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}^{\phi}(u), \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}^{\phi}(v)\} \\ \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(s \odot t) &\geq \min\{\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(\phi(u)), \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(\phi(v))\} \\ \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(s \odot t) &\geq \min\{\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(s), \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(t)\},\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(s \odot t) &= \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(\phi(u \odot v)) \\ \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(s \odot t) &= \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}^{\phi}(u \odot v) \\ \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(s \odot t) &\leq \max\{\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}^{\phi}(u), \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}^{\phi}(v)\} \\ \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(s \odot t) &\leq \max\{\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(\phi(u)), \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(\phi(v))\} \\ \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(s \odot t) &\leq \max\{\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(s), \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(t)\}.\end{aligned}$$

Hence $\mathcal{A} = (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}})$ is a single-valued neutrosophic K -subalgebra of \mathcal{K}_2 . \square

From above two propositions we obtain the following theorem.

Theorem 2.7. Let $\phi : \mathcal{K}_1 \rightarrow \mathcal{K}_2$ be an epimorphism of K -algebras. Then $\mathcal{A}^{\phi} = (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}^{\phi}, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}^{\phi}, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}^{\phi})$ is a single-valued neutrosophic K -subalgebra of \mathcal{K}_1 if and only if $\mathcal{A} = (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}})$ is a single-valued neutrosophic K -subalgebra of \mathcal{K}_2 .

Definition 2.7. A single-valued neutrosophic K -subalgebra $\mathcal{A} = (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}})$ of a K -algebra \mathcal{K} is called *characteristic* if $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(\phi(s)) = \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(s)$, $\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(\phi(s)) = \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(s)$ and $\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(\phi(s)) = \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(s)$, for all $s \in G$ and $\phi \in \text{Aut}(\mathcal{K})$.

Definition 2.8. A K -subalgebra S of a K -algebra \mathcal{K} is said to be *fully invariant* if $\phi(S) \subseteq S$, for all $\phi \in \text{End}(\mathcal{K})$, where $\text{End}(\mathcal{K})$ is the set of all endomorphisms of a K -algebra \mathcal{K} . A single-valued neutrosophic K -subalgebra $\mathcal{A} = (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}})$ of a K -algebra \mathcal{K} is called *fully invariant* if $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(\phi(s)) \leq \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(s)$, $\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(\phi(s)) \leq \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(s)$ and $\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(\phi(s)) \leq \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(s)$, for all $s \in G$ and $\phi \in \text{End}(\mathcal{K})$.

Definition 2.9. Let $\mathcal{A}_1 = (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}_1}, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}_1}, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}_1})$ and $\mathcal{A}_2 = (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}_2}, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}_2}, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}_2})$ be single-valued neutrosophic K -subalgebras of \mathcal{K} . Then $\mathcal{A}_1 = (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}_1}, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}_1}, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}_1})$ is said to be the same type of $\mathcal{A}_2 = (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}_2}, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}_2}, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}_2})$ if there exist $\phi \in \text{Aut}(\mathcal{K})$ such that $\mathcal{A}_1 = \mathcal{A}_2 \circ \phi$, i.e., $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}_1}(s) = \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}_2}(\phi(s))$, $\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}_1}(s) = \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}_2}(\phi(s))$ and $\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}_1}(s) = \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}_2}(\phi(s))$, for all $s \in G$.

Theorem 2.8. Let $\mathcal{A}_1 = (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}_1}, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}_1}, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}_1})$ and $\mathcal{A}_2 = (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}_2}, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}_2}, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}_2})$ be single-valued neutrosophic K -subalgebras of \mathcal{K} . Then $\mathcal{A}_1 = (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}_1}, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}_1}, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}_1})$ is a single-valued neutrosophic K -subalgebra having the same type of $\mathcal{A}_2 = (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}_2}, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}_2}, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}_2})$ if and only if \mathcal{A}_1 is isomorphic to \mathcal{A}_2 .

Proof. Sufficient condition holds trivially so we only need to prove the necessary condition. Let $\mathcal{A}_1 = (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}_1}, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}_1}, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}_1})$ be a single-valued neutrosophic K -subalgebra having same type of $\mathcal{A}_2 = (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}_2}, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}_2}, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}_2})$. Then there exist $\phi \in \text{Aut}(\mathcal{K})$ such that $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}_1}(s) = \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}_2}(\phi(s))$, $\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}_1}(s) = \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}_2}(\phi(s))$ and $\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}_1}(s) = \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}_2}(\phi(s))$, for all $s \in G$. Let $f : \mathcal{A}_1(K) \rightarrow \mathcal{A}_2(K)$ be a mapping defined by $f(\mathcal{A}_1(s)) = \mathcal{A}_2(\phi(s))$, for all $s \in G$, that is,

$f(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}_1}(s)) = \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}_2}(\phi(s))$, $f(\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}_1}(s)) = \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}_2}(\phi(s))$ and $f(\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}_1}(s)) = \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}_2}(\phi(s))$, for all $s \in G$.
Clearly, f is surjective. Also, f is injective because if $f(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}_1}(s)) = f(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}_1}(t))$, for all $s, t \in G$, then $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}_2}(\phi(s)) = \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}_2}(\phi(t))$ and we have $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}_1}(s) = \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}_1}(t)$. Similarly, $\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}_1}(s) = \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}_1}(t)$, $\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}_1}(s) = \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}_1}(t)$.
Therefore, f is a homomorphism, for $s, t \in G$

$$\begin{aligned} f(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}_1}(s \odot t)) &= \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}_2}(\phi(s \odot t)) = \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}_2}(\phi(s) \odot \phi(t)), \\ f(\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}_1}(s \odot t)) &= \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}_2}(\phi(s \odot t)) = \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}_2}(\phi(s) \odot \phi(t)), \\ f(\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}_1}(s \odot t)) &= \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}_2}(\phi(s \odot t)) = \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}_2}(\phi(s) \odot \phi(t)). \end{aligned}$$

Hence $\mathcal{A}_1 = (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}_1}, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}_1}, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}_1})$ is isomorphic to $\mathcal{A}_2 = (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}_2}, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}_2}, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}_2})$. Hence the proof. \square

3 (\tilde{a}, \tilde{b}) -Single-Valued Neutrosophic K -Algebras

Definition 3.1. A single-valued neutrosophic set $\mathcal{A} = (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}})$ in a set G is called an (\tilde{a}, \tilde{b}) -single-valued neutrosophic K -subalgebra of \mathcal{K} if it satisfy the following conditions:

- $u_{(\alpha_1, \beta_1, \gamma_1)} \tilde{a} \mathcal{A}$, $v_{(\alpha_2, \beta_2, \gamma_2)} \tilde{a} \mathcal{A} \Rightarrow (u \odot v)_{(\min(\alpha_1, \alpha_2), \min(\beta_1, \beta_2), \max(\gamma_1, \gamma_2))} \tilde{b} \mathcal{A}$,
for all $u, v \in G$, $\alpha_1, \alpha_2 \in (0, 1]$, $\beta_1, \beta_2 \in (0, 1]$, $\gamma_1, \gamma_2 \in [0, 1]$.

Twelve different types of single-valued neutrosophic K -subalgebras can be obtained by replacing the values of $\tilde{a} (\neq \in \wedge q)$ and \tilde{b} by any two values in the set $\{\in, q, \in \vee q, \in \wedge q\}$ in Definition 1.1.

Remark 3.1. Every (\in, \in) -single-valued neutrosophic K -subalgebra is in fact, a single-valued neutrosophic K -subalgebra.

Proposition 3.1. Every (\in, \in) -single-valued neutrosophic K -subalgebra is an $(\in, \in \vee q)$ -single-valued neutrosophic K -subalgebra.

Proof. Let $\mathcal{A} = (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}})$ be a single-valued neutrosophic K -subalgebra of \mathcal{K} . Let $u, v \in G$ and $\alpha_1, \alpha_2 \in (0, 1]$, $\beta_1, \beta_2 \in (0, 1]$, $\gamma_1, \gamma_2 \in [0, 1]$ be such that $u_{(\alpha_1, \beta_1, \gamma_1)} \in \mathcal{A}$, $v_{(\alpha_2, \beta_2, \gamma_2)} \in \mathcal{A}$. Then $u_{(\alpha_1, \beta_1, \gamma_1)} \in \mathcal{A}$, $v_{(\alpha_2, \beta_2, \gamma_2)} \in \mathcal{A} \Rightarrow (u \odot v)_{(\min(\alpha_1, \alpha_2), \min(\beta_1, \beta_2), \max(\gamma_1, \gamma_2))} \in \vee q \mathcal{A}$. Hence \mathcal{A} is an $(\in, \in \vee q)$ -single-valued neutrosophic K -subalgebra of \mathcal{K} . \square

Proposition 3.2. Every $(\in \vee q, \in \vee q)$ -single-valued neutrosophic K -subalgebra is an $(\in, \in \vee q)$ -single-valued neutrosophic K -subalgebra of \mathcal{K} .

Definition 3.2. Let $\mathcal{A} = (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}})$ is a single-valued neutrosophic set in G . The set $\underline{\mathcal{A}} = \{u \in G \mid \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(u) \neq 0, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(u) \neq 0, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(u) \neq 0\}$ is called the *support* of \mathcal{A} .

Lemma 3.1. If $\mathcal{A} = (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}})$ is a non-zero (\in, \in) -single-valued neutrosophic K -subalgebra of \mathcal{K} , then $\underline{\mathcal{A}}$ is a K -subalgebra of \mathcal{K} .

Proof. Let $\mathcal{A} = (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}})$ is a non-zero (\in, \in) -single-valued neutrosophic K -subalgebra of \mathcal{K} and let $u, v \in \underline{\mathcal{A}}$. Then $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(u) \neq 0$ and $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(v) \neq 0$, $\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(u) \neq 0$ and $\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(v) \neq 0$ and $\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(u) \neq 0$, $\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(v) \neq 0$. If $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(u \odot v) = 0$, $\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(u \odot v) = 0$ and $\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(u \odot v) = 0$. Since $u_{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}}(u) \in \mathcal{A}$ and $v_{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}}(v) \in \mathcal{A}$, $u_{\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}}(u) \in \mathcal{A}$ and $v_{\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}}(v) \in \mathcal{A}$, $u_{\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}}(u) \in \mathcal{A}$ and $v_{\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}}(v) \in \mathcal{A}$ but

$$(u \odot v)_{(\min(\mathcal{T}_A(u), \mathcal{T}_A(v)), \min(\mathcal{I}_A(u), \mathcal{I}_A(v)), \max(\mathcal{F}_A(u), \mathcal{F}_A(v)))} \notin \mathcal{A}.$$

Since $\mathcal{T}_A(u \odot v) = 0, \mathcal{I}_A(u \odot v) = 0$ and $\mathcal{F}_A(u \odot v) = 0$. A contradiction. Hence $\mathcal{T}_A(u \odot v) \neq 0, \mathcal{I}_A(u \odot v) \neq 0$ and $\mathcal{F}_A(u \odot v) \neq 0$ which shows that $(u \odot v) \in \underline{\mathcal{A}}$, consequently $\underline{\mathcal{A}}$ is a K-subalgebra of \mathcal{A} . \square

Lemma 3.2. If $\mathcal{A} = (\mathcal{T}_A, \mathcal{I}_A, \mathcal{F}_A)$ is a non-zero (\in, q) -single-valued neutrosophic K-subalgebra of \mathcal{K} , then $\underline{\mathcal{A}}$ is a K-subalgebra of \mathcal{K} .

Lemma 3.3. If $\mathcal{A} = (\mathcal{T}_A, \mathcal{I}_A, \mathcal{F}_A)$ is a non-zero (q, \in) -single-valued neutrosophic K-subalgebra of \mathcal{K} , then $\underline{\mathcal{A}}$ is a K-subalgebra of \mathcal{K} .

Lemma 3.4. If $\mathcal{A} = (\mathcal{T}_A, \mathcal{I}_A, \mathcal{F}_A)$ is a non-zero (q, q) -single-valued neutrosophic K-subalgebra of \mathcal{K} , then $\underline{\mathcal{A}}$ is a K-subalgebra of \mathcal{K} .

The proof of above three lemmas is followed by Definitions.

Theorem 3.1. If $\mathcal{A} = (\mathcal{T}_A, \mathcal{I}_A, \mathcal{F}_A)$ is a non-zero (\tilde{a}, \tilde{b}) -single-valued neutrosophic K-subalgebra of \mathcal{K} , then $\underline{\mathcal{A}}$ is a K-subalgebra of \mathcal{K} .

Definition 3.3. A neutrosophic set $\mathcal{A} = (\mathcal{T}_A, \mathcal{I}_A, \mathcal{F}_A)$ in a K-algebra \mathcal{K} is called an $(\in, \in \vee q)$ -single-valued neutrosophic K-subalgebra of \mathcal{K} if it satisfy the following conditions:

- (a) $e_{(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)} \in \mathcal{A} \Rightarrow (u)_{(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)} \in \vee q \mathcal{A}$,
- (b) $u_{(\alpha_1, \beta_1, \gamma_1)} \in \mathcal{A}, v_{(\alpha_2, \beta_2, \gamma_2)} \in \mathcal{A} \Rightarrow (u \odot v)_{(\min(\alpha_1, \alpha_2), \min(\beta_1, \beta_2), \max(\gamma_1, \gamma_2))} \in \vee q \mathcal{A}$,

For all $u, v \in G, \alpha, \alpha_1, \alpha_2 \in (0, 1], \beta, \beta_1, \beta_2 \in (0, 1], \gamma, \gamma_1, \gamma_2 \in [0, 1)$.

Example 3.1. Consider a K-algebra $\mathcal{K} = (G, \cdot, \odot, e)$, where

$G = \{e, x, x^2, x^3, x^4, x^5, x^6\}$ is the cyclic group of order 7 and Caley's table for \odot is given as:

\odot	e	x	x^2	x^3	x^4	x^5	x^6
e	e	x^6	x^5	x^4	x^3	x^2	x
x	x	e	x^6	x^5	x^4	x^3	x^2
x^2	x^2	x	e	x^6	x^5	x^4	x^3
x^3	x^3	x^2	x	e	x^6	x^5	x^4
x^4	x^4	x^3	x^2	x	e	x^6	x^5
x^5	x^5	x^4	x^3	x^2	x	e	x^6
x^6	x^6	x^5	x^4	x^3	x^2	x	e

We define a single-valued neutrosophic set $\mathcal{A} = (\mathcal{T}_A, \mathcal{I}_A, \mathcal{F}_A)$ in \mathcal{K} as follows:

$$\mathcal{T}_A(u) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } u = e, \\ 0.7 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$$\mathcal{I}_A(u) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } u = e, \\ 0.6 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$$\mathcal{F}_A(u) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } u = e, \\ 0.5 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Now take

$$\alpha = 0.4, \alpha_1 = 0.5, \alpha_2 = 0.3,$$

$$\beta = 0.5, \beta_1 = 0.6, \beta_2 = 0.3,$$

$$\gamma = 0.6, \gamma_1 = 0.6, \gamma_2 = 0.5, \text{ where}$$

$$\alpha, \alpha_1, \alpha_2 \in (0, 1], \beta, \beta_1, \beta_2 \in (0, 1], \gamma, \gamma_1, \gamma_2 \in [0, 1).$$

By direct calculations, it is easy to see that \mathcal{A} is an $(\in, \in \vee q)$ -single-valued neutrosophic K-subalgebra of \mathcal{K} .

Theorem 3.2. Let $\mathcal{A} = (\mathcal{T}_A, \mathcal{I}_A, \mathcal{F}_A)$ be a single-valued neutrosophic set in \mathcal{K} . Then \mathcal{A} is an $(\in, \in \vee q)$ -single-valued neutrosophic K-subalgebra of \mathcal{K} if and only if

$$\begin{aligned} \text{(i)} \quad & \mathcal{T}_A(u) \geq \min(\mathcal{T}_A(e), 0.5), \\ & \mathcal{I}_A(u) \geq \min(\mathcal{I}_A(e), 0.5), \\ & \mathcal{F}_A(u) \leq \max(\mathcal{F}_A(e), 0.5). \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{(ii)} \quad & \mathcal{T}_A(u \odot v) \geq \min(\mathcal{T}_A(u), \mathcal{T}_A(v), 0.5), \\ & \mathcal{I}_A(u \odot v) \geq \min(\mathcal{I}_A(u), \mathcal{I}_A(v), 0.5), \\ & \mathcal{F}_A(u \odot v) \leq \max(\mathcal{F}_A(u), \mathcal{F}_A(v), 0.5), \text{ for all } u, v \in G. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let us assume that \mathcal{A} is an $(\in, \in \vee q)$ -single-valued neutrosophic K-subalgebra.

(ii) \Rightarrow (i): Let for $u, v \in G$. Assume that $\mathcal{T}_A(u \odot v) < \min(\mathcal{T}_A(u), \mathcal{T}_A(v), 0.5)$, $\mathcal{I}_A(u \odot v) < \min(\mathcal{I}_A(u), \mathcal{I}_A(v), 0.5)$, $\mathcal{F}_A(u \odot v) > \max(\mathcal{F}_A(u), \mathcal{F}_A(v), 0.5)$. Then $\mathcal{T}_A(u \odot v) < \min(\mathcal{T}_A(u), \mathcal{T}_A(v))$, $\mathcal{I}_A(u \odot v) < \min(\mathcal{I}_A(u), \mathcal{I}_A(v))$ and $\mathcal{F}_A(u \odot v) > \max(\mathcal{F}_A(u), \mathcal{F}_A(v))$. Take α, β, γ such that

$\mathcal{T}_A(u \odot v) < \alpha < \min(\mathcal{T}_A(u), \mathcal{T}_A(v)$, $\mathcal{I}_A(u \odot v) < \beta < \min(\mathcal{I}_A(u), \mathcal{I}_A(v)$, $\mathcal{F}_A(u \odot v) > \gamma > \max(\mathcal{F}_A(u), \mathcal{F}_A(v)$. Then $u_\alpha, v_\alpha \in \mathcal{T}_A$, $u_\beta, v_\beta \in \mathcal{I}_A$ and $u_\gamma, v_\gamma \in \mathcal{F}_A$ but $(u \odot v)_{(\min(\alpha_1, \alpha_2), \min(\beta_1, \beta_2), \max(\gamma_1, \gamma_2))} \notin \overline{\vee q} \mathcal{A}$, a contradiction.

Assume that $\mathcal{T}_A(u \odot v) < 0.5$, $\mathcal{I}_A(u \odot v) < 0.5$, $\mathcal{F}_A(u \odot v) > 0.5$. Then $u_{(0.5, 0.5, 0.5)}, v_{(0.5, 0.5, 0.5)} \in \mathcal{A}$, but $(u \odot v)_{(0.5, 0.5, 0.5)} \notin \overline{\vee q} \mathcal{A}$ which is also a contradiction. Hence (i) holds.

Let $u_{(\alpha_1, \beta_1, \gamma_1)}, v_{(\alpha_2, \beta_2, \gamma_2)} \in \mathcal{A}$ which means that $\mathcal{T}_A(u) \geq \alpha_1, \mathcal{T}_A(v) \geq \alpha_2, \mathcal{I}_A(u) \geq \beta_1, \mathcal{I}_A(v) \geq \beta_2$,

$\mathcal{F}_A(u) \leq \gamma_1, \mathcal{F}_A(v) \leq \gamma_2$. We have $\mathcal{T}_A(u \odot v) \geq \min(\mathcal{T}_A(u), \mathcal{T}_A(v), 0.5) \geq \min(\alpha_1, \alpha_2, 0.5)$,

$\mathcal{I}_A(u \odot v) \geq \min(\mathcal{I}_A(u), \mathcal{I}_A(v), 0.5) \geq \min(\beta_1, \beta_2, 0.5)$, $\mathcal{F}_A(u \odot v) \leq \max(\mathcal{F}_A(u), \mathcal{F}_A(v), 0.5) \leq \max(\gamma_1, \gamma_2, 0.5)$.

If $\min(\alpha_1, \alpha_2) > 0.5, \min(\beta_1, \beta_2) > 0.5, \max(\gamma_1, \gamma_2) < 0.5$, then $\mathcal{T}_A(u \odot v) \geq 0.5 \Rightarrow \mathcal{T}_A(u \odot v) + \min(\alpha_1, \alpha_2) > 1$, $\mathcal{I}_A(u \odot v) \geq 0.5 \Rightarrow \mathcal{I}_A(u \odot v) + \min(\beta_1, \beta_2) > 1$, $\mathcal{F}_A(u \odot v) \leq 0.5 \Rightarrow \mathcal{F}_A(u \odot v) + \max(\gamma_1, \gamma_2) < 1$.

But if $\min(\alpha_1, \alpha_2) \leq 0.5, \min(\beta_1, \beta_2) \leq 0.5, \max(\gamma_1, \gamma_2) \geq 0.5$, then $\mathcal{T}_A(u \odot v) \geq \min(\alpha_1, \alpha_2)$,

$\mathcal{I}_A(u \odot v) \geq \min(\beta_1, \beta_2)$, $\mathcal{F}_A(u \odot v) \leq \max(\gamma_1, \gamma_2)$. Hence $(u \odot v)_{(\min(\alpha_1, \alpha_2), \min(\beta_1, \beta_2), \max(\gamma_1, \gamma_2))} \in \vee q \mathcal{A}$. Which completes the proof. \square

Theorem 3.3. Let $\mathcal{A} = (\mathcal{T}_A, \mathcal{I}_A, \mathcal{F}_A)$ be a single-valued neutrosophic set in \mathcal{K} . Then \mathcal{A} is an $(\in, \in \vee q)$ -single-valued neutrosophic K-subalgebra of \mathcal{K} if and only if each non-empty $\mathcal{A}_{(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)}$ is a K-subalgebra of \mathcal{K} . For $\alpha, \beta \in (0.5, 1], \gamma \in [0.5, 1)$.

Proof. Assume that $\mathcal{A} = (\mathcal{T}_A, \mathcal{I}_A, \mathcal{F}_A)$ is an $(\in, \in \vee q)$ -single-valued neutrosophic K-subalgebra of \mathcal{K} and let $\alpha, \beta \in (0.5, 1], \gamma \in [0.5, 1)$. To prove that $\mathcal{A}_{(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)} = \{u \in G \mid \mathcal{T}_A(u) \geq \alpha, \mathcal{I}_A(u) \geq \beta, \mathcal{F}_A(u) \leq \gamma\}$ is a K-subalgebra of \mathcal{K} . If $u, v \in \mathcal{A}_{(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)}$, then $\mathcal{T}_A(u) \geq \alpha, \mathcal{T}_A(v) \geq \alpha, \mathcal{I}_A(u) \geq \beta, \mathcal{I}_A(v) \geq \beta, \mathcal{F}_A(u) \leq \gamma, \mathcal{F}_A(v) \leq \gamma$. Thus, $\mathcal{T}_A(e) \geq \min(\mathcal{T}_A(u), 0.5) \geq \min(\alpha, 0.5) = \alpha, \mathcal{I}_A(e) \geq \min(\mathcal{I}_A(u), 0.5) \geq \min(\beta, 0.5) = \beta$, $\mathcal{F}_A(e) \leq \max(\mathcal{F}_A(u), 0.5) \geq \min(\gamma, 0.5) = \gamma$ and $\mathcal{T}_A(u \odot v) \geq \min(\mathcal{T}_A(u), \mathcal{T}_A(v), 0.5) \geq \min(\alpha, 0.5) = \alpha$, $\mathcal{I}_A(u \odot v) \geq \min(\mathcal{I}_A(u), \mathcal{I}_A(v), 0.5) \geq \min(\beta, 0.5) = \beta$, $\mathcal{F}_A(u \odot v) \leq \max(\mathcal{F}_A(u), \mathcal{F}_A(v), 0.5) \leq \max(\gamma, 0.5) = \gamma$. Thus, $u \odot v \in \mathcal{A}_{(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)}$. Hence $\mathcal{A}_{(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)}$ is a K-subalgebra of \mathcal{K} . Converse part is obvious. \square

Theorem 3.4. Let $\mathcal{A} = (\mathcal{T}_A, \mathcal{I}_A, \mathcal{F}_A)$ be a single-valued neutrosophic set in \mathcal{K} . Then $\mathcal{A}_{(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)}$ is a K-subalgebra of \mathcal{K} if and only if

$$\begin{aligned} \text{(a)} \quad & \max(\mathcal{T}_A(u \odot v), 0.5) \geq \min(\mathcal{T}_A(u), \mathcal{T}_A(v)), \\ & \max(\mathcal{I}_A(u \odot v), 0.5) \geq \min(\mathcal{I}_A(u), \mathcal{I}_A(v)), \\ & \min(\mathcal{F}_A(u \odot v), 0.5) \leq \max(\mathcal{F}_A(u), \mathcal{F}_A(v)), \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{(b)} \quad & \max(\mathcal{T}_A(e), 0.5) \geq \mathcal{T}_A(u), \\ & \max(\mathcal{I}_A(e), 0.5) \geq \mathcal{I}_A(u), \\ & \min(\mathcal{F}_A(e), 0.5) \leq \mathcal{F}_A(u), \text{ for all } u, v \in G. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Suppose that $\mathcal{A}_{(\alpha,\beta,\gamma)}$ is a K-subalgebra of \mathcal{K} and let $\max(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(u \odot v), 0.5) < \min(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(u), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(v)) = \alpha$, $\max(\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(u \odot v), 0.5) < \min(\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(u), \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(v)) = \beta$, $\min(\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(u \odot v), 0.5) > \max(\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(u), \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(v)) = \gamma$. Then for $\alpha, \beta \in (0.5, 1]$ and $\gamma \in [0.5, 1)$ and $u, v \in \mathcal{A}_{(\alpha,\beta,\gamma)}$, $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(u \odot v) < \alpha$, $\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(u \odot v) < \beta$, $\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(u \odot v) > \gamma$. Since $u, v \in \mathcal{A}_{(\alpha,\beta,\gamma)}$ and $\mathcal{A}_{(\alpha,\beta,\gamma)}$ is a K-subalgebra of \mathcal{K} , so $u, v \in \mathcal{A}_{(\alpha,\beta,\gamma)}$ or $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(u \odot v) \geq \alpha$, $\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(u \odot v) \geq \beta$, $\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(u \odot v) \leq \gamma$. Which is a contradiction. Conversely, suppose that conditions (a) and (b) holds. Assume that $\alpha, \beta \in (0.5, 1], \gamma \in [0.5, 1)$, for $u, v \in \mathcal{A}_{(\alpha,\beta,\gamma)}$. Then we have $0.5 < \alpha \leq \min(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(u), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(v)) \leq \max(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(u \odot v), 0.5) \Rightarrow \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(u \odot v) \geq \alpha$, $0.5 < \beta \leq \min(\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(u), \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(v)) \leq \max(\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(u \odot v), 0.5) \Rightarrow \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(u \odot v) \geq \beta$, $0.5 > \gamma \geq \max(\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(u), \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(v)) \geq \min(\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(u \odot v), 0.5) \Rightarrow \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(u \odot v) \leq \gamma$. $0.5 < \alpha \leq \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(u) \leq \max(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(e), 0.5) \Rightarrow \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(mu) \geq \alpha$, $0.5 < \beta \leq \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(u) \leq \max(\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(e), 0.5) \Rightarrow \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(mu) \geq \beta$, $0.5 > \gamma \geq \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(u) \geq \min(\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(e), 0.5) \Rightarrow \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(mu) \leq \gamma$, for some $m \in G$ $u \odot v \in \mathcal{A}_{(\alpha,\beta,\gamma)}$. Hence $\mathcal{A}_{(\alpha,\beta,\gamma)}$ is a K-subalgebra of \mathcal{K} . \square

Theorem 3.5. The intersection of any family of $(\in, \in \vee q)$ -single-valued neutrosophic K-subalgebra of \mathcal{K} is an $(\in, \in \vee q)$ -single-valued neutrosophic K-subalgebra of \mathcal{K} .

Proof. Let $\{\mathcal{A}_j : j \in I\}$ be a family of $(\in, \in \vee q)$ -single-valued neutrosophic K-subalgebras of \mathcal{K} .

Let $\mathcal{A} = \bigcap_{j \in I} \mathcal{A}_j = (\sup_{j \in I} \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}_j}, \sup_{j \in I} \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}_j}, \inf_{j \in I} \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}_j})$, for $u, v \in G$ we have

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(u \odot v) &\geq \min(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(u), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(v), 0.5), \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(u \odot v) \geq \min(\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(u), \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(v), 0.5), \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(u \odot v) \leq \max(\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(u), \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(v), 0.5). \\ \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(u \odot v) &= \sup_{j \in I} \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}_j}(u \odot v) \\ \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(u \odot v) &\geq \sup_{j \in I} \min(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}_j}(u), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}_j}(v), 0.5) \\ \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(u \odot v) &= \min(\sup_{j \in I} \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}_j}(u), \sup_{j \in I} \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}_j}(v), 0.5) \\ \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(u \odot v) &= \min(\bigcap_{j \in I} \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}_j}(u), \bigcap_{j \in I} \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}_j}(v), 0.5) \\ \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(u \odot v) &= \min(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(u), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(v), 0.5), \\ \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(u \odot v) &= \sup_{j \in I} \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}_j}(u \odot v) \\ \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(u \odot v) &\geq \sup_{j \in I} \min(\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}_j}(u), \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}_j}(v), 0.5) \\ \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(u \odot v) &= \min(\sup_{j \in I} \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}_j}(u), \sup_{j \in I} \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}_j}(v), 0.5) \\ \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(u \odot v) &= \min(\bigcap_{j \in I} \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}_j}(u), \bigcap_{j \in I} \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}_j}(v), 0.5) \\ \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(u \odot v) &= \min(\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(u), \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(v), 0.5), \\ \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(u \odot v) &= \inf_{j \in I} \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}_j}(u \odot v) \\ \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(u \odot v) &\leq \inf_{j \in I} \max(\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}_j}(u), \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}_j}(v), 0.5) \\ \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(u \odot v) &= \max(\inf_{j \in I} \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}_j}(u), \inf_{j \in I} \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}_j}(v), 0.5) \\ \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(u \odot v) &= \max(\bigcap_{j \in I} \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}_j}(u), \bigcap_{j \in I} \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}_j}(v), 0.5) \\ \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(u \odot v) &= \max(\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(u), \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(v), 0.5). \end{aligned}$$

It follows that \mathcal{A} is an $(\in, \in \vee q)$ -single-valued neutrosophic K-subalgebra of \mathcal{K} . \square

Definition 3.4. Let $\epsilon_1, \epsilon_2 \in [0, 1]$ and $\epsilon_1 < \epsilon_2$. Let $\mathcal{A} = (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}})$ is a single-valued neutrosophic K-subalgebra of \mathcal{K} . Then \mathcal{A} is called a single-valued neutrosophic K-subalgebra with thresholds (ϵ_1, ϵ_2) of \mathcal{K} if

$$\begin{aligned} \max(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(u \odot v), \epsilon_1) &\geq \min(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(u), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(v), \epsilon_2), \\ \max(\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(u \odot v), \epsilon_1) &\geq \min(\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(u), \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}(v), \epsilon_2), \\ \min(\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(u \odot v), \epsilon_1) &\leq \max(\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(u), \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}(v), \epsilon_2), \text{ for all } u, v \in G. \end{aligned}$$

Example 3.2. Using example 2.1, it is easy to see that $\mathcal{A} = (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}})$ is a single-valued neutrosophic K-subalgebra with thresholds $(\epsilon_1 = 0.3, \epsilon_2 = 0.56)$ and for $(\epsilon_1 = 0.55, \epsilon_2 = 0.78)$.

Remark 3.2. Let for $\epsilon_1, \epsilon_2 \in [0, 1]$ and $\epsilon_1 < \epsilon_2$ unless otherwise specified.

(i) When $\epsilon_1 = 0$ and $\epsilon_2 = 1$ in single-valued neutrosophic K-subalgebra with thresholds (ϵ_1, ϵ_2) , \mathcal{A} is an ordinary single-valued neutrosophic K-subalgebra.

(2) When $\epsilon_1 = 0$ and $\epsilon_2 = 0.5$ in single-valued neutrosophic K-subalgebra with thresholds (ϵ_1, ϵ_2) , \mathcal{A} is an $(\in, \in \vee q)$ -single-valued neutrosophic K-subalgebra.

Theorem 3.6. A single-valued neutrosophic set \mathcal{A} in \mathcal{K} is a single-valued neutrosophic K-subalgebra with thresholds (ϵ_1, ϵ_2) if and only if

$\cup(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}, \alpha), \cup(\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}, \beta), L(\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}, \gamma) (\neq \phi), \alpha, \beta, \gamma \in (\epsilon_1, \epsilon_2]$ is a K-subalgebra of \mathcal{K} .

Proof. Assume that \mathcal{A} is a single-valued neutrosophic K-subalgebra with thresholds (ϵ_1, ϵ_2) . First to prove that $\cup(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}, \alpha)$ is a K-subalgebra of \mathcal{K} , let $u, v \in \cup(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}, \alpha)$. Then $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(u) \geq \alpha$ and $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(v) \geq \alpha, \alpha \in (\epsilon_1, \epsilon_2]$. Since \mathcal{A} is a single-valued neutrosophic K-subalgebra. It follows that

$$\max(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(u \odot v), \epsilon_1) \geq \min(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(u), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(v), \epsilon_2) = \alpha,$$

so that $u \odot v \in \cup(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}, \alpha)$. Hence $\cup(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}, \alpha)$ is a k-subalgebra of \mathcal{K} . Similarly, we can proof for $\cup(\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}, \beta)$ and $L(\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}, \gamma)$. Hence $\mathcal{A}_{(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)}$ is a K-subalgebra of \mathcal{K} .

Conversely, consider that a single-valued neutrosophic set \mathcal{A} be such that $\mathcal{A}_{(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)} \neq \phi$ is a K-subalgebra of \mathcal{K} for $(\epsilon_1, \epsilonpsilon_2) \in [0, 1]$ and $(\epsilon_1 < \epsilon_2)$. Suppose that $\max(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(u \odot v), \epsilon_1) < \min(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(u), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(v), \epsilon_2) = \alpha$, then $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(u \odot v) < \alpha, u \in \cup(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}, \alpha), v \in \cup(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}, \alpha), \alpha \in (\epsilon_1, \epsilon_2]$. Since $u, v \in \cup(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}, \alpha)$ and $\cup(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}, \alpha)$ is a K-subalgebra, $u \odot v \in \cup(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}, \alpha)$, i.e., $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{A}}(u \odot v) \geq \alpha$, a contradiction. Similar results can be obtained for $\cup(\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}, \beta)$ and $L(\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{A}}, \gamma)$. \square

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